

Chemistry of Terminalia Species. Part IV. Chemical Examination of *T. Arjuna* Bedd: Isolation of Arjunolic Acid Saponin and (+) Leucodelphinidin

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From acetone extract of the heartwood of *T. arjuna*, a complex saponin of arjunolic acid and (+)-leucodelphinidin have been isolated.

Recent studies on the heartwood of *T. arjuna* led to the isolation of β -sitosterol, oleanolic acid, and arjunolic acid besides a small amount of ellagic acid from the ether extract¹. The wood was not examined further for alcohol or acetone extractives. In view of the therapeutic importance of the *T. arjuna* bark², the heartwood as well as the bark was again taken up for systematic examination.

The heartwood was obtained from a large tree on the banks of the river "Godavari" near Rajahmundry. From petroleum ether extract of the heartwood, β -sitosterol, but no oleanolic acid, could be isolated (cf. King *et al.*¹). The ether extract deposited arjunolic acid (I) as the chief component. It was identified by comparison with an authentic sample from *T. tomentosa*³. A minor component of the ether extract was ellagic acid.

The acetone extract deposited a brown solid on keeping at 0° for several days. It could be readily separated into two fractions with ethyl acetate. The larger insoluble fraction (2.5 g.) crystallised from acetone as light brown crystals, m.p. 216-20°, and gave all the characteristic reactions of a triterpene carboxylic acid. From its solubility and analysis it appeared to be a saponin. Acid hydrolysis led to the formation of arjunolic acid (I) and *d*-glucose only (identified through glucosazone and R_f value 0.25). Analysis suggests that it might be a diglucoside of arjunolic acid. In a quantitative hydrolysis with acids, only about 45% of arjunolic acid could be recovered along with an uncrystallisable brown residue.

1. King *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3995; 1958, 2830.

2. Kirtiker and Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants", 1933, pp. 1023-1028.

3. Ramachandra Row and Subba Rao, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1960, No. 27, 12.

The ethyl acetate-soluble fraction answered all the characteristic colour reactions of a leuco-anthocyanidin. It was carefully purified by countercurrent distribution using five separatory funnels according to the method of Bush and Denson⁴. The pure compound had all the characteristics of (+)-leucodelphinidin (m.p. 245-48° decomp.); methyl ether m.p. 186-87°, $[\alpha]_D^{30} +70^\circ$; acetate m.p. 246-48°. It gave the characteristic cherry-red colour with vanillin-HCl in the cold and blue ferric reaction. Further confirmation was provided by the oxidation of the methyl ether to trimethylgallic acid with permanganate.

Leucodelphinidin has been previously noticed in *Eucalyptus* Kino gum (*Eucalyptus pitulana*) and in the bark of *Phyllanthus emblica*⁵.

EXPERIMENTAL*

Extraction of the Heartwood of T. Arjuna.—The light brown heartwood powder (2 kg.) was successively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°), ether, and acetone in a Soxhlet extractor. The light yellow petroleum ether extract on concentration deposited a pale yellow solid (compound A) (2 g.).

During extraction with ether, a white crystalline powder (15 g.) separated. Some more (5 g.) of the solid was secured on complete removal of the solvent. The total solid was dissolved in hot acetic acid and filtered. The filtrate, on careful dilution with water, deposited a solid which crystallised from ethanol as colorless prisms (16 g.), m. p. 320-24° (compound B).

The acetic acid-insoluble residue was crystallised as pale yellow solid (compound C), yield 0.5 g.

The acetone extract was concentrated to a small volume (75 ml), diluted with ether (300 ml), and kept in the frigidaire for about a week, when a brown solid separated. It was collected and extracted with small quantities of ethyl acetate in the cold. The ethyl acetate-insoluble portion (compound D) was crystallised from methanol as colorless solid, m.p. 214-16°, yield 2.5 g.

The dry ethyl acetate extract was concentrated and precipitated with light petroleum ether. The process was repeated till a colorless solid (compound E) was obtained; yield 2.65 g.

The filtrate from the acetone extract on further concentration did not deposit any more of the solid.

Identification of Compound (A): β -Sitosterol.—Compound (A) was further crystallised twice from methanol when it came out as fine needles, m.p. 136-37°, undepressed with authentic β -sitosterol; $[\alpha]_D^{30} -35^\circ$ (c. 0.8 in chloroform). (Found: C, 84.01; H, 12.26. Calc. for $C_{29}H_{50}O$: C, 84.04; H, 12.06%).

The acetate crystallised from methanol as needles, m.p. 126-27°, undepressed with authentic β -sitosterol acetate.

4. *Anal. Chem.*, 1948, 20, 121.

5. Ganguly *et al.*, *Tetrahedron*, 1958, 3, 225; Lannas and Seshadri, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1958, 17B, 169.

*M.P.s are not corrected. All compounds were dried at 100° / 0.1 mm for 6-8 hrs. for analysis.

Examination of Compound (B): Arjunolic Acid.—Compound (B) was crystallised several times from acetone when it came out as shining microprisms, m. p. 332-34°, undepressed with authentic arjunolic acid, isolated from *Terminalia tomentosa*; $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 63^\circ$ (c, 0.51 in ethanol). (Found: C, 73.67; H, 9.47. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{48}O_5$: C, 73.73; H, 9.9%).

The methyl ester (with ethereal diazomethane) crystallised from methanol as needles, m. p. 209-11°, undepressed with authentic methyl arjunolate; $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 62^\circ$ (c, 1.57 in chloroform).

The bromolactone (m. p. 240°; $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 53^\circ$) and the isolactone (m. p. 265-66°; $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 16^\circ$) were identical with the corresponding derivatives of arjunolic acid.

Examination of Compound (C): Ellagic Acid.—Compound (C) crystallised from dioxan as a pale yellow solid which did not melt below 360°. It gave a green colour with ethanolic ferric chloride and responded to the Griesmayer reaction and was found identical with ellagic acid. (The tetramethyl ether m. p. 341-43° and tetracetate m. p. 340-44°).

Examination of Compound (D): Arjunolic Acid Saponin.—Compound (D) is sparingly soluble in acetone and methanol. It crystallised from ethanol as amorphous powder (2.0 g.), m. p. 216-20°; $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 86^\circ$ (c, 0.32 in ethanol). (Found: C, 62.21; H, 8.6. $C_{42}H_{60}O_{15}$ requires C, 62.04; H 8.37%). Compound (D) is soluble in NaOH and gave no colour with ethanolic ferric chloride.

Hydrolysis of Compound (D): Arjunolic Acid.—Compound (D) (500 mg.) was refluxed for 4 hrs. with 4% methanolic sulphuric acid. During hydrolysis a light brown solid separated. It was filtered after cooling and the filtrate was extracted continuously with ether to recover more of the solid. It crystallised from acetone as microprisms (120 mg.), m. p. 332-34°; methyl ester m. p. 209-11°, undepressed by an authentic sample of arjunolic acid. (Found: C, 73.90; H, 9.5. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{48}O_5$: C, 73.73; H, 9.9%).

The filtrate, after removing arjunolic acid, was neutralised with barium carbonate and after filtering the inorganic salts, it was concentrated in *vacuo* at 45° to a small volume (30 ml). It gave a crystalline osazone, m. p. 201-204°, identified as glucosazone. Ascending paper chromatography with butanol-acetic acid-water (4:1:5) showed only one spot having an R_f value 0.25; under similar conditions glucose has an R_f value 0.26.

Examination of Compound (E): (+)-Leucodelphinidin.—Compound (E) (1.0 g.) was further purified according to the method of Bush and Densen⁴ by distribution between ethyl acetate and water using five separatory funnels. The solvent was removed from the ethyl acetate fractions and the compound crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether whereby the pure leuco-anthocyanidin was obtained as a colorless, amorphous powder (120 mg.), m. p. 245-48° (decomp.). (Found: C, 52.62, 52.03; H, 4.62, 4.42. $C_{15}H_{14}O_8$, 1 H_2O requires C, 52.9; H, 4.7%).

Compound (E) is readily soluble in NaOH and gave a blue colour with a faint green tint with ethanolic ferric chloride. With warm 10% EtOH-HCl the compound developed a bright red colour which wholly went into amyl alcohol, forming a deep red solution. The compound gave a cherry-red colour with vanillin and hydrochloric acid in the cold instantaneously.

Methyl ether (diazomethane) crystallised as pale yellow plates from methanol, m.p. 186-87°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} +70^\circ$ (c , 1.2 in ethanol). (Found: C, 61.13; H, 6.48; OMe, 39.22. $C_{20}H_{24}O_8$ requires C, 61.20; H, 6.2; OMe, 39.54%).

The acetate (acetic anhydride-pyridine) came out as colorless microcrystals from petroleum ether, m.p. 246-48°. (Found: C, 56.27; H, 4.72. $C_{29}H_{26}O_{13}$ requires C, 56.5; H, 4.5%).

Potassium Permanganate Oxidation of the Methyl Ether.—The methyl ether of compound (E) (100 mg.) in dry acetone solution (30 ml) was oxidised with an excess of permanganate (500 mg.) by refluxing for 6 hrs. The ether-soluble fraction was sublimed at 160°/0.1 mm and crystallised from hot water. *O*-Trimethylgallic acid was obtained as colorless needles, m.p. 165-68°, undepressed with an authentic sample.

Conversion of Compound (E) into Delphinidin Chloride.—A mixture of the leuco-anthocyanidin (500 mg.) and sodium acetate (1 g.) in water (10 ml) was boiled for 10 mins. Freshly fused zinc chloride (1 g.) was then added and the mixture boiled for a minute more. The reaction mixture was then cooled, treated with a saturated solution of picric acid (5 ml), and the mixture heated under reflux for 10 mins. Ethanolic hydrochloric acid (50 ml, 8%) was added to the reaction mixture and heating under reflux continued for 2 hrs. The mixture was diluted with water, kept in the frigidaire for 2 to 3 hrs, and the reddish brown mass (phlobaphene) filtered. The clear filtrate was then treated with isoamyl alcohol (20 ml). The anthocyanidin was transferred to 1% aqueous HCl by the addition of light petroleum ether. With ferric chloride a blue colour with a faint green tinge, with sodium acetate, a pure blue, and with sodium carbonate a bluish violet precipitate were noticed⁵.

Circular paper chromatography indicated a faint ring (R_f 0.48) with a butanol-acid-water mixture (4:1:5) and the spot was developed with bromophenol blue⁵.

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